

On the Second Order Mannheim Partner Curve in E^3

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Abstract: In this study first we worked on the Mannheim curve pair $\{\alpha, \alpha_1\}$ and Mannheim curve pair $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2\}$. We called α_2 as the second order Mannheim partner curve of the Mannheim curve α . We examined the Frenet apparatus of second order Mannheim partner curve in terms of, Frenet apparatus of Mannheim curve α , with the offset property of second order Mannheim partner α_2 . Further we examined third order Mannheim partner α_3 where $\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\}$ are Mannheim curve pair.

Key Words: Mannheim curve, Frenet apparatus, second Mannheim curve, modified Darboux vector.

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§1. Introduction

Mannheim curve was firstly defined by A. Mannheim in 1878. A curve is called a Mannheim curve if and only if $\frac{\kappa}{\kappa^2 + \tau^2}$ is a nonzero constant, κ is the curvature and τ is the torsion. Mannheim curve was redefined in [6], if the principal normal vector N of first curve and binormal vector B_1 of second curve are linearly dependent, then first curve is called Mannheim curve, and the second curve is called Mannheim partner curve. As a result they called these new curves as Mannheim partner curves. For more detail see in [6]. Frenet-Serret apparatus of the curve $\alpha : I \rightarrow E^3$ are $\{T, N, B, \kappa, \tau\}$. For any unit speed curve α , the Darboux and modified Darboux vectors are, respectively ([2],[4])

$$D(s) = \tau(s)T(s) + \kappa(s)B(s), \quad (1.1)$$

$$\tilde{D}(s) = \frac{\tau}{\kappa}(s)T(s) + B(s). \quad (1.2)$$

In [7] Mannheim curves are studied and Mannheim partner curve of α can be represented

$$\alpha(s_1) = \alpha_1(s_1) + \lambda(s_1)B_1(s_1) \quad (1.3)$$

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for some function λ , since N and B_1 are linearly dependent, equation can be rewritten as

$$\alpha_1(s) = \alpha(s) - \lambda(s)N(s), \quad (1.4)$$

where

$$\lambda(s) = \frac{-\kappa(s)}{(\kappa(s))^2 + (\tau(s))^2}. \quad (1.5)$$

Frenet-Serret apparatus of Mannheim partner curve α_1 are $\{T_1, N_1, B_1, \kappa_1, \tau_1\}$. The relationship α and α_1 Frenet vectors are as follows

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 &= \cos \theta T - \sin \theta B \\ N_1 &= \sin \theta T + \cos \theta B \\ B_1 &= N. \end{aligned} \quad (1.6)$$

where $\angle(T, T_1) = \cos \theta$. The first curvature and the second curvature (torsion) are

$$\kappa_1 = -\frac{d\theta}{ds_1} = \frac{\theta'}{\cos \theta}, \quad \tau_1 = \frac{\kappa}{\lambda\tau}. \quad (1.7)$$

We use dot \cdot to denote the derivative with respect to the arc length parameter of the curve α . Also

$$\frac{ds}{ds_1} = \frac{1}{\cos \theta} = \frac{-\lambda\tau_1}{\sin \theta}, \quad (1.8)$$

for more detail see in [7], or we can write

$$\frac{ds}{ds_1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \lambda\tau}}. \quad (1.9)$$

§2. Second Order Mannheim Partner and Frenet Apparatus

Definition 2.1 Let $\{\alpha, \alpha_1\}$ and $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2\}$ be the Mannheim pairs of α and α_1 respectively. We called as α_2 is a second order Mannheim partner of the curve α . which has the following parametrization ,

$$\alpha_2 = \alpha + \lambda_1 \sin \theta T - \lambda N + \lambda_1 \cos \theta B, \quad (2.1)$$

where

$$\alpha_1 = \alpha(s) - \lambda N(s) \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha_2 = \alpha_1(s) - \lambda_1 N_1(s). \quad (2.2)$$

Theorem 2.1 The Frenet vectors of second order Mannheim partner α_2 of a Mannheim curve

α , based on the Frenet apparatus of Mannheim curve α are

$$\begin{cases} T_2 = \cos \theta_1 \cos \theta T - \sin \theta_1 N - \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta B \\ N_2 = \sin \theta_1 \cos \theta T + \cos \theta_1 N - \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta B \\ B_2 = \sin \theta T + \cos \theta B. \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

Proof Let α_2 be second order Mannheim partner of a Mannheim curve α . Also α_2 be the Mannheim partner of Mannheim partner α_1 . The Frenet vector fields T_1, N_1, B_1 and T_2, N_2, B_2 which are belong to the curves α_1 and α_2 , respectively. It is easy to say that Frenet vectors of second order Mannheim partner α_2 , based on the Frenet vectors of Mannheim curve α_1 are

$$\begin{cases} T_2 = \cos \theta_1 T_1 - \sin \theta_1 B_1 \\ N_2 = \sin \theta_1 T_1 + \cos \theta_1 B_1 \\ B_2 = N_1 \end{cases}$$

where $\angle(T_1, T_2) = \theta_1$. By substituting T_1, N_1, B_1 we have the equalities in terms of the curve α .

$$\begin{aligned} T_2 &= \cos \theta_1 (\cos \theta T - \sin \theta B) - \sin \theta_1 N \\ N_2 &= \sin \theta_1 (\cos \theta T - \sin \theta B) + \cos \theta_1 N \\ B_2 &= \sin \theta T + \cos \theta B \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. Also the following product give us the same equalities;

$$\begin{bmatrix} T_2 \\ N_2 \\ B_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_1 & 0 & -\sin \theta_1 \\ \sin \theta_1 & 0 & \cos \theta_1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & -\sin \theta \\ \sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T \\ N \\ B \end{bmatrix}. \quad \square$$

Theorem 2.2 Let α_2 be second order Mannheim partner of a Mannheim curve α . The curvature and torsion of the second order Mannheim partner α_2 are

$$\kappa_2 = \frac{-\theta'_1}{\cos \theta \cos \theta_1}, \quad \tau_2 = \frac{-\theta'}{\cos \theta} \frac{\lambda \tau}{\lambda_1 \kappa}. \quad (2.4)$$

Proof Since $\kappa_1 = \frac{-\theta'}{\cos \theta}$ and $\tau_1 = \frac{\kappa}{\lambda \tau}$, we have the curvature as in the following way

$$\kappa_2 = -\frac{d\theta_1}{ds_2} = \frac{-\theta'_1}{\cos \theta \cos \theta_1}.$$

Also as in the following way we have the torsion

$$\tau_2 = \frac{\kappa_1}{\lambda_1 \tau_1} = \frac{-\theta'}{\cos \theta} \frac{\lambda \tau}{\lambda_1 \kappa}.$$

We use mark to denote the derivative with respect to the parameter of the curve α . Due

to this theorem we also get

$$\frac{ds}{ds_2} = \frac{1}{\cos \theta \cos \theta_1}. \quad (2.5)$$

□

Theorem 2.3 *The modified Darboux vector of Mannheim partner α_1 of a Mannheim curve α , is*

$$\tilde{D}_1(s) = \frac{\kappa \cos^2 \theta}{\lambda \tau \theta'} T + N - \frac{\kappa \cos \theta \sin \theta}{\lambda \tau \theta'} B \quad (2.6)$$

Proof Similarly from the equation (1.2)

$$\tilde{D}_1(s) = \frac{\tau_1}{\kappa_1} T_1(s) + B_1(s). \quad (2.7)$$

Substituting the equation (2.7) into equation (1.6) and (1.7), the proof is complete. □

Theorem 2.4 *The modified Darboux vector of second order Mannheim partner α_2 of a Mannheim curve α , is*

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{D}_2 = & \left(\frac{\lambda \tau \cos^2 \theta_1 \cos \theta}{\lambda_1 \kappa} + \sin \theta \right) T - \frac{\lambda \tau \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta_1}{\lambda_1 \kappa} N \\ & - \left(\frac{\lambda \tau \cos^2 \theta_1 \sin \theta}{\lambda_1 \kappa} - \cos \theta \right) B. \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

Proof Since

$$\tilde{D}_2(s) = \frac{\tau_2}{\kappa_2} T_2(s) + B_2(s). \quad (2.9)$$

Substituting the equation (2.9) into equation (2.3) and (2.4), the proof is complete. □

Theorem 2.5 *The offset property of second order Mannheim partner α_2 can be given if and only if the curvature κ and the torsion τ of α satisfy the following equation*

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{-\theta' \tau \cos \theta}{\theta'^2 \tau + (\kappa^2 + \tau^2)^2 \cos^2 \theta}, \quad (2.10)$$

where $\theta'^2 \tau + (\kappa^2 + \tau^2)^2 \cos^2 \theta \neq 0$.

Proof Notice that $\kappa_1 = \frac{-\theta'}{\cos \theta}$, $\tau_1 = \frac{\kappa}{\lambda \tau}$ with the offset property $-\kappa_1 = \lambda_1 (\kappa_1^2 + \tau_1^2)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} (\kappa_1^2 + \tau_1^2) &= \frac{-\kappa_1}{\lambda_1} \\ \lambda_1 &= \frac{-\theta'}{\cos \theta} \frac{1}{\theta'^2 \tau + \cos^2 \theta (\kappa^2 + \tau^2)^2} \\ & \quad \frac{\tau \cos^2 \theta}{\tau \cos^2 \theta} \\ \lambda_1 &= \frac{-\theta' \tau \cos \theta}{\theta'^2 \tau + (\kappa^2 + \tau^2)^2 \cos^2 \theta}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 2.6 *The second order Mannheim partner α_2 is not a Mannheim partner curve α .*

Proof Since the definition of Mannheim partner curve,

$$\langle B_2(s), N(s) \rangle = \langle \sin \theta T + \cos \theta B, N \rangle = 0,$$

hence $N(s)$ and $B_2(s)$ are linear independent. \square

Definition 2.2 *Let $\{\alpha, \alpha_1\}$, $\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2\}$ and $\{\alpha_2, \alpha_3\}$ be the Mannheim pairs of α , α_1 and α_2 respectively. We called as α_3 is a third order Mannheim partner of the curve α , which has the following parametrizations,*

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_3(s) &= \alpha_2(s) - \lambda_2 N_2(s) \\ &= \alpha + (\lambda_1 \sin \theta + \lambda_2 \sin \theta_1 \cos \theta) T - (\lambda - \lambda_2 \cos \theta_1) N \\ &\quad + (\lambda_1 \cos \theta - \lambda_2 \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta) B, \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

where

$$\alpha_2 = \alpha + \lambda_1 \sin \theta T - \lambda N + \lambda_1 \cos \theta B \quad (2.12)$$

and

$$|\lambda + \lambda_1 + \lambda_2|$$

is the distance between the arlengthed curves α and α_3 .

Theorem 2.7 *The Frenet vectors of third order Mannheim partner α_3 of a Mannheim curve α , based on the Frenet apparatus of Mannheim curve α are*

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} T_3 = (\cos \theta_2 \cos \theta_1 \cos \theta - \sin \theta_2 \sin \theta) T - \cos \theta_2 \sin \theta_1 N \\ \quad - (\sin \theta_2 \cos \theta + \cos \theta_2 \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta) B \\ N_3 = (\sin \theta_2 \cos \theta_1 \cos \theta + \cos \theta_2 \sin \theta) T - \sin \theta_2 \sin \theta_1 N \\ \quad + (\cos \theta_2 \cos \theta - \sin \theta_2 \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta) B \\ B_3 = \sin \theta_1 \cos \theta T + \cos \theta_1 N - \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta B \end{array} \right. \quad (2.13)$$

where $\angle(T_2, T_3) = \cos \theta_2$.

Proof Since

$$\begin{bmatrix} T_3 \\ N_3 \\ B_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_2 & 0 & -\sin \theta_2 \\ \sin \theta_2 & 0 & \cos \theta_2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_1 & 0 & -\sin \theta_1 \\ \sin \theta_1 & 0 & \cos \theta_1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ \times \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & -\sin \theta \\ \sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T \\ N \\ B \end{bmatrix},$$

we have the proof. \square

Corollary 2.1 *The product of Frenet vector fields of third order Mannheim partner α_3 and Mannheim curve α , has the following matrix form*

$$[\mathbf{V}_3]^T [\mathbf{V}] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_2 \cos \theta_1 \cos \theta & -\cos \theta_2 \sin \theta_1 & -\sin \theta_2 \cos \theta \\ -\sin \theta_2 \sin \theta & & -\cos \theta_2 \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta \\ \sin \theta_2 \cos \theta_1 \cos \theta & -\sin \theta_2 \sin \theta_1 & \cos \theta_2 \cos \theta \\ +\cos \theta_2 \sin \theta & & -\sin \theta_2 \cos \theta_1 \sin \theta \\ \sin \theta_1 \cos \theta & \cos \theta_1 & -\sin \theta_1 \sin \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.14)$$

where $[\mathbf{V}_3] = [T_3, N_3, B_3]$ and $[\mathbf{V}] = [T, N, B]$.

Corollary 2.2 *Let α_3 be third order Mannheim partner of a Mannheim curve α . The curvature and torsion of the third order Mannheim partner α_3 are*

$$\kappa_3 = -\frac{\theta_2'}{\cos \theta \cos \theta_1 \cos \theta_2}, \quad \tau_3 = \frac{\theta_1' \lambda_1 \kappa}{\theta' \cos \theta_1 \lambda_2 \lambda \tau}. \quad (2.15)$$

Proof We can write

$$\kappa_3 = -\frac{d\theta_2}{ds_3} = \frac{-\theta_2'}{\cos \theta \cos \theta_1 \cos \theta_2}$$

and

$$\tau_3 = \frac{\kappa_2}{\lambda_2 \tau_2} = \frac{\theta_1' \lambda_1 \kappa}{\theta' \cos \theta_1 \lambda_2 \lambda \tau}$$

or also since

$$\cos \theta \cos \theta_1 \cos \theta_2 = \frac{-\theta_2'}{\kappa_3}$$

and

$$\cos \theta \cos \theta_1 = \frac{-\theta_1'}{\kappa_2}. \quad \square$$

References

- [1] Boyer C., *A History of Mathematics*, Wiley, New York 1968.
- [2] Gray A., *Modern Differential Geometry of Curves and Surfaces with Mathematica*, 2nd ed. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, p. 205, 1997.
- [3] Hacısalıhoğlu H.H., *Differential Geometry(in Turkish)* , İnönü University Publications, Malatya, vol.1, 1994.
- [4] Izumiya S., Takeuchi N., Special curves and ruled surfaces, *Beitr age zur Algebra und Geometrie Contributions to Algebra and Geometry*, Vol.44, No.1(2003), 203-212.
- [5] Lipschutz M.M., *Differential Geometry*, Schaum's Outlines.
- [6] Liu H., Wang F., Mannheim partner curves in 3-space, *Journal of Geometry*, Vol.88, No.1-2(2008), 120-126(7).
- [7] Orbay K., Kasap E., On Mannheim partner curves E^3 , *International Journal of Physical Sciences*, Vol.4, No.5(2009), 261-264.
- [8] McCleary J., *Geometry From a Differentiable View Point*, Vassar Collage, Cambridge University Press 1994.
- [9] Schief W.K., On the integrability of Bertrand curves and Razzaboni surfaces, *Journal of Geometry and Physics*, Vol.45, No.1-2(2003), 130-150.